

Coding Performance Impact on a Constant-Weight Predictor for CCSDS 123.0-B-2

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- **Introduction**
- **Proposal**
- **Experimental Results**
- **Conclusions**

CCSDS 123.0-B-2

CCSDS 123.0-B-2

$$\mathbf{U}_z(t) = \begin{bmatrix} d_z^N(t) \\ d_z^W(t) \\ d_z^{NW}(t) \\ d_{z-1}(t) \\ d_{z-2}(t) \\ \vdots \\ d_{z-P_z^*}(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{W}_z(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_z^N(t) \\ \omega_z^W(t) \\ \omega_z^{NW}(t) \\ \omega_z^{(1)}(t) \\ \omega_z^{(2)}(t) \\ \vdots \\ \omega_z^{(P_z^*)}(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\hat{d}_z(t) = \mathbf{W}_z^T(t) \mathbf{U}_z(t)$$

CCSDS 123.0-B-2

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$$\hat{d}_z(t) = \mathbf{W}_z^T(t) \mathbf{U}_z(t)$$

$$\omega_z^{(i)}(t+1) = \text{clip} \left(\omega_z^{(i)}(t) + \lfloor \frac{1}{2} (\text{sgn}^+[e_z(t)] \cdot 2^{-(\rho(t)+\zeta_z^{(i)})} \cdot d_{z-i}(t) + 1) \rfloor, \{\omega_{\min}, \omega_{\max}\} \right)$$

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This inner product and updating is high computation demand!!

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Can it be skipped?

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- Tune properly some parameters of the predictor:

$$\zeta_z^{(i)} = \zeta_z^* = 5$$

$$\nu_{\min} = \nu_{\max} = 9$$

$$\Omega \leq 11$$

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- At this way $\mathbf{W}_z^T(t)$ remains constant and the inner product can be skipped
- This speeds up the predictor stage but does not predict the samples so accurately

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$\mathbf{W}_z^T(t)$ needs to be previously set

Coding performance penalty

Fast Mode

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Strategy 1

Strategy 1

Strategy 2 (lossless and near-lossless)

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	Regular Mode	Fast Mode	Fast Mode'
Hyperion			
PAE = 0	5.27	5.54	5.54
PAE = 1	3.64	3.96	3.95
PAE = 3	2.52	2.81	2.79
PAE = 7	1.62	1.86	1.89
PAE = 15	0.97	1.12	1.16
PAE = 31	0.54	0.62	0.68
Airs			
PAE = 0	7.43	7.53	7.53
PAE = 1	5.87	5.97	5.97
PAE = 3	4.79	4.84	4.84
PAE = 7	3.77	3.83	3.83
PAE = 15	2.79	2.83	2.83
PAE = 31	1.88	1.89	1.91
Avisis			
PAE = 0	7.36	7.30	7.30
PAE = 1	5.83	5.77	5.78
PAE = 3	4.69	4.61	4.62
PAE = 7	3.76	3.67	3.67
PAE = 15	2.96	2.86	2.89
PAE = 31	2.28	2.18	2.28
Modis			
PAE = 0	7.27	7.53	7.53
PAE = 1	5.75	6.00	6.01
PAE = 3	4.63	4.88	4.89
PAE = 7	3.69	3.89	3.93
PAE = 15	2.87	3.02	3.04
PAE = 31	2.14	2.25	2.27

Strategy 2 (lossless and near-lossless)

	Regular Mode	Fast Mode	Fast Mode'
Hyperion			
PAE = 0	5.27	5.54	5.54
PAE = 1	3.64	3.96	3.95
PAE = 3	2.52	2.81	2.79
PAE = 7	1.62	1.86	1.89
PAE = 15	0.97	1.12	1.16
PAE = 31	0.54	0.62	0.68
Airs			
PAE = 0	7.43	7.53	7.53
PAE = 1	5.87	5.97	5.97
PAE = 3	4.79	4.84	4.84
PAE = 7	3.77	3.83	3.83
PAE = 15	2.79	2.83	2.83
PAE = 31	1.88	1.89	1.91
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PAE = 1	5.83	5.77	5.78
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PAE = 7	3.76	3.67	3.67
PAE = 15	2.96	2.86	2.89
PAE = 31	2.28	2.18	2.28
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PAE = 31	2.14	2.25	2.27

Strategy 3 (lossless and near-lossless)

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	Regular Mode	Fast Mode	Overhead
Hyperion			
PAE = 0	5.27	5.53	5.00%
PAE = 1	3.70	3.95	6.71%
PAE = 3	2.58	2.81	8.90%
PAE = 7	1.67	1.91	13.91%
PAE = 15	0.99	1.15	15.80%
PAE = 31	0.55	0.69	25.78%
Airs			
PAE = 0	7.43	7.58	2.12%
PAE = 1	5.87	6.02	2.59%
PAE = 3	4.79	4.88	1.88%
PAE = 7	3.77	3.88	3.08%
PAE = 15	2.79	2.88	3.61%
PAE = 31	1.88	1.94	3.45%
Aviris			
PAE = 0	7.36	7.38	0.91%
PAE = 1	5.87	5.86	0.31%
PAE = 3	4.75	4.68	-1.31%
PAE = 7	3.82	3.70	-3.30%
PAE = 15	3.02	2.99	-0.17%
PAE = 31	2.33	2.40	7.29%
Modis			
PAE = 0	8.17	8.30	1.58%
PAE = 1	6.66	6.78	1.92%
PAE = 3	5.53	5.67	2.56%
PAE = 7	4.57	4.68	2.52%
PAE = 15	3.71	3.79	2.18%
PAE = 31	2.86	2.94	2.95%

Strategy 3 (lossless and near-lossless)

	Regular Mode	Fast Mode	Overhead
Hyperion			
PAE = 0	5.27	5.53	5.00%
PAE = 1	3.70	3.95	6.71%
PAE = 3	2.58	2.81	8.90%
PAE = 7	1.67	1.91	13.91%
PAE = 15	0.99	1.15	15.80%
PAE = 31	0.55	0.69	25.78%
Airs			
PAE = 0	7.43	7.58	2.12%
PAE = 1	5.87	6.02	2.59%
PAE = 3	4.79	4.88	1.88%
PAE = 7	3.77	3.88	3.08%
PAE = 15	2.79	2.88	3.61%
PAE = 31	1.88	1.94	3.45%
Aviris			
PAE = 0	7.36	7.38	0.91%
PAE = 1	5.87	5.86	0.31%
PAE = 3	4.75	4.68	-1.31%
PAE = 7	3.82	3.70	-3.30%
PAE = 15	3.02	2.99	-0.17%
PAE = 31	2.33	2.40	7.29%
Modis			
PAE = 0	8.17	8.30	1.58%
PAE = 1	6.66	6.78	1.92%
PAE = 3	5.53	5.67	2.56%
PAE = 7	4.57	4.68	2.52%
PAE = 15	3.71	3.79	2.18%
PAE = 31	2.86	2.94	2.95%

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- Tuning some parameters of the coding process of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 predictor the prediction weight stage can be skipped.
- This fact allows to speed the coding process at expenses of coding performance penalization.
- Encode the first 40 lines updating the weights and the rest in Fast Mode, produce a penalization from 1% to 5%.
- Competitive coding performance is also obtained when the weights are built with a training image, and the trained weights are used to compress another scene of the same sensor using the Fast Mode.
 - Overheads between 1% and 5% for lossless.
 - Penalty augments as the quantization step increases.

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